

JAVIST scanning

– A tool for business service and product development

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“The development of the scanning tool has been a genuine example of sharing knowledge. We have combined research-based knowledge and the expertise of the academic community with the views of various experts in the City organisation and the needs of businesses in our meetings and workshops. I strongly believe that, through these collaborative settings, our project will result in an increasingly effective and impactful ecosystem that supports the development of business operations in the sector.” – Marjo Kenttälä, Business Helsinki

Summary

The Resourceful Sharing: Co-usable Innovation and Learning Environments (JAVIST) project focuses on business and research collaboration which has been carried out in the context of learning and innovation environments. The project has resulted in a scanning tool called JAVIST, enabling businesses to review the relevance of their innovations at different stages of product and service development, as well as the related experience of place and principles of shared space. The JAVIST scanning tool combines a three-perspective model where the experience of place and its relevance to science education and shared use are described by statements on dimensions pertaining to individuals, groups and the broader societal context.

With the help of these statements, the JAVIST tool can be used to collect quantitative and qualitative data to support product development and collect feedback. The tool is suitable for innovation and learning environments as well as digital, physical and social services supporting learning.

- 1. Assessing and developing solutions:**

The scanning tool enables businesses to test and assess their innovative products and services in genuine environments, such as physical and digital learning environments. The tool offers evidence-based models that help assess solutions from pedagogical, ecological, financial and social perspectives.

- 2. Supporting co-creation:**

The tool enables the participation of various stakeholders (businesses, universities, municipalities, users) in co-creation and experimentation. It helps to identify user needs and develop solutions based on these needs.

- 3. Measuring impact:**

The scanning tool helps measure the utilisation rate and impact of learning and innovation environments.

The indicators include qualitative and quantitative methods, such as user tours, interviews, surveys and statistical analyses.

- 4. Supporting scalability:**

The tool enables businesses to develop solutions that are reproducible and scalable for domestic and international markets.

The data produced by it support the alignment and faster deployment of business processes.

- 5. Supporting continuous improvement:**

The validation tool is suitable for use as part of iterative development processes where solutions can be continuously improved based on collected data.

What and for whom?

- Businesses: The tool provides concrete means and methods for developing and assessing solutions, as well as boosts competitiveness in the market.
- **Organisations for education and research:** The tool promotes research-based development and validation as well as increases collaboration with businesses.
- **Municipalities and public administration:** The tool improves the management of shared facilities and helps to optimise resource use.
- Users (teachers, learners): The tool improves the functionality and user experience of digital and physical learning environments.

1. Background for the JAVIST scanning tool

New learning and innovation environments are user-oriented entities designed and implemented by several operators. They are associated with physical and digitalised separate or mixed elements. Their use is characterised by sharing and continuous development. Services that support and enable learning are growing in importance.

In the Resourceful Sharing project, the JAVIST scanning tool was created for businesses to review the input of their products through three different perspectives when developing a product and drawing up communications plans:

1. The experienced relevance (significance) of learning
2. The experience of place in learning environments
3. Practices of shared use and sharing in physical and digital learning environments

2. Purpose of the JAVIST scanning tool

The purpose of the scanning tool is to help developers of learning and innovation environments to review the features of their products in relation to user experience, pedagogical relevance and shared-use practices.

With the help of the scanning tool, developers of solutions and services will gain inspiration for design, communication and feedback collection from aspects that research has shown to be significant in responsible new learning environments.

The tool includes a set of statements in Finnish and English. In practice, tool users gain content from these statements for their own user surveys and themes for any workshops they organise to support product development. The statements are supplemented by a workshop bank that utilises service design methods. These tools provide businesses and stakeholders with versatile ways to develop and assess products and services.

3. Context and content of the JAVIST scanning tool

The research-based focus of the JAVIST scanning tool has been the relevance of science education, experiences of the digital or physical learning environments in use, as well as perspectives on their shared use and sharing. When integrating these perspectives into a single model, the challenge has been to identify the differences and similarities between physical and

digital learning environments. This applies to both the experience of place as well as the practices of sharing and shared use. The strength of integration comes down to the identification of the three overlapping perspectives: in the first perspective, individual experience, the relevance of learning content and the significance of shared use are immediately evident. Individual experience determines motivation and commitment. The second perspective focuses more on the level where identifiable groups operate and normalise their activities. The social reference group can be a school class, people pursuing the same profession, or another group formed based on a common practice that affects the behaviour and experiences of individuals. The third perspective, known as the societal perspective, represents a broader context to which the relevance of the topic of learning, the significance of the spatial experience as well as the practices of sharing and shared use leave their mark. Matters relevant to many veers towards a broader context, turning into phenomena, places, situations or events of significance. This entity is described in the adjacent JAVIST triangle (Figure 1).

Figure 1 JAVIST-model.

Next, we take a closer look at the three corners of the JAVIST triangle:

1. The experienced relevance of learning
2. The experience of place in learning environments
3. Collaborative sharing

3.1 The experienced relevance of learning

In connection with science education provided by the University of Helsinki, a great deal of research has been conducted on the relevance of learning solutions experienced by learners. This research utilises what is known as a relevance model, which examines experienced relevance from personal, societal and vocational perspectives at the same time. Motivational factors can be intrinsic or extrinsic, and they can be temporal either in the present or the future (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Experienced relevance (applied from Stuckey et al., 2013).

Personal relevance refers to learners' personal interests or curiosity. From the perspective of vocational relevance, learners are interested in, for example, their future employment. Societal relevance refers to how meaningful learners perceive innovations to society or how interaction with innovations helps learners find a meaningful role in society. Prior research leads to the conclusion that many learning solutions support personal interests without taking into account vocational or societal dimensions. These dimensions should be strengthened to make learners understand the potential of the topic of the learning solution (e.g., a discipline, art, physical activity) for future employment and its significance as part of society. Taking this into consideration in the design and development of innovations in businesses can provide an advantage compared to similar products and services from the perspective of experienced relevance.

For example, the relevance of science education in chemistry is supported, among other things, by designing new learning materials that introduce societally significant solutions produced by chemistry. Development is carried out in cooperation with research groups at the Department of Chemistry of the University of Helsinki, enabling learners to meet junior researchers working in the field. They also serve as role models for young people and may inspire careers in science. Further information on the scholarly background of relevance in use cases is available, for example, in studies conducted by Pernaa et al. (2021, 2022, 2023).

The following table presents the relevance statements of the scanning tool (Table 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**). The statements were originally developed for a study on science education in chemistry, investigating experienced relevance among comprehensive school pupils from grades 7 to 9 as they explored molecular modelling as a teaching method (Pernaa et al. 2023). They have been adjusted for the JAVIST tool collaboratively with businesses using iterative workshops, as described in section **Error! Reference source not found.**. Detailed instructions for using the statements are available in section 4.

Table 1 The statements for investigating the relevance of the solution.

#	Level	Statements
1	PR	Using <i>the solution</i> (or Visiting <i>the learning environment</i>) increased my interest in <i>the topic</i> .
2	PR	While using <i>the solution</i> (or During the visit) I learned things that helped me better understand the topics taught at school.
3	PR	While using <i>the solution</i> (or During the visit) I learned things that will be useful to me in the future.
4	PR	Using <i>the solution</i> (or Visiting <i>the learning environment</i>) was interesting.
5	PR	I would like to use <i>the solution</i> (or visit <i>the learning environment</i>) again.
6	PR (negat.)	I think <i>the solution</i> was difficult to use (or it was difficult to operate <i>in the learning environment</i>).
7	PR	Using <i>the solution</i> (or Visiting <i>the learning environment</i>) helped me understand the world better.
8	SR	I learned teamwork skills while using <i>the solution</i> (or during the visit).
9	SR	I learned about the importance of <i>the topic</i> for society.
10	SR	Using <i>the solution</i> (or The visit) made me appreciate <i>the field of _____</i> more.
11	SR (negat.)	I don't understand why <i>this solution (or learning environment)</i> is needed in society.
12	SR	<i>This solution (or learning environment)</i> is important for scientific research.
13	SR	<i>This solution (or learning environment)</i> promotes sustainable development.
14	VR (negat.)	Using <i>the solution</i> (or Visiting <i>the learning environment</i>) did not teach me any new skills.
15	VR	<i>The solution (or Visiting the learning environment)</i> gave me new information about jobs in the field.
16	VR	<i>Using the solution (or Visiting the learning environment)</i> may influence my career choice.
17	VR	I will use <i>this solution (or learning environment)</i> in my future studies or profession.
18	VR (negat.)	Using <i>the solution (or learning environment)</i> is useless for me in the future.
19	VR	Using <i>the solution (or learning environment)</i> includes creative work.
20	VR	<i>This solution (or learning environment)</i> is an important tool for <i>the field of _____</i> .

3.2 The experience of place in learning environments

Research on learning environments has investigated physical and digital environments. The physical built environment comprises places and locations such as schools, classrooms, museums or, for example, the technology container developed by the City of Helsinki through co-creation with its partners in the Resourceful Sharing project. At the same time, physical spaces lead to digital environments: learning games, virtual reality and collaboration platforms where experiences, documents and skills can be shared. The elements of user experience can be examined in these environments through six dimensions:

1. Tune (atmosphere)
2. Tempo(rality)
3. Task (functionality)
4. Tie (familiarity)
5. Tale (narrative)
6. Theme (significance)

These constitute the 6T model for the experience of place (Figure 3Error! Reference source not found.).

Figure 3. 6T-model of place experience (applied from Nenonen & Kojo, 2013).

The 6T model was created at Aalto University in cooperation with several disciplines and businesses. It has been tested in a range of work and learning environments as well as digital spaces. The experience of place in urban areas has also been analysed (Nenonen et al. 2013; Tähtinen et al., 2013; Kojo & Nenonen 2016; Puro 2022). The model has been used in several development projects, including the [House of Experiences project](#) (link in Finnish only).

Tune and tempo in places

When entering a space, two dimensions of the experience of place in the 6T model are quickly perceived. First, the individual uses all their senses to make unconscious observations about the atmosphere of the place: the space feels like something, they can smell its indoor air, hear its acoustics, see its colours. People have also learned to sense the atmosphere in digital environments where they rely primarily on sight and hearing. Seeing faces and exchanging greetings affect the atmosphere. Digital environments can also be decorated with background images to convey a range of atmospheres. Background images or game landscapes generate atmospheres, meanings as well as memory traces for those digitally present in the space.

The temporality of place is a close pair to its atmosphere. The furniture can communicate assumptions of spending time in the space. For example, the tables and chairs in fast food restaurants indicate that the idea is not to stay for a long time. Clocks visible in offices, health centres or schools indicate time management, which may affect experiences of the temporality of the place. Physical spaces are associated with learned temporal practices, which are in fact inappropriate for digital environments. For example, it has been observed that the practice of commencing classes 15 minutes past the hour at universities is reduced to roughly three minutes in meetings. Transitions from one digital situation to another have also become very rapid as digital environments become increasingly common.

The following table presents the scanning tool statements for the first two dimensions of the experience of place: tune and tempo (Table 2).

Table 2 The statements connected to the tune and tempo of the physical or digital experience of place.

#	Focus	PHYSICAL	DIGITAL
1	6TX	The atmosphere <i>here</i> is nice.	It is easy to connect to <i>the platform/digital environment/innovation</i> .
2	6TX	It looks comfortable <i>here</i> .	<i>The platform</i> looks inviting.
3	6TX	Time flies <i>here</i> .	It is easy to navigate on <i>the platform</i> .
4	6TX	It is easy to start to study <i>here</i> .	The visualization is clear.

Task and tie in the experience of place

The experience of functionality reflects whether learners using the space can do the tasks they intended to do. Functionality can be examined by asking what works in the space and how suitable it is for specific tasks. The adaptability of places to various functions is also part of their functionality. It is important to consider the smooth progress of synchronous multi-location work in the planning of places. How should display screens be placed in meetings with both remote and on-site participants so that everyone can see them equally well? It is important to perceive places as 360-degree environments. Older features, such as the stand and projection screen in front of a traditional classroom, must be avoided in environments that integrate physical and digital spaces.

The dimension of familiarity indicates whether people are used to using spaces and how they are able to operate in them. Spaces also provide tips on how to behave in them. Learners can experience using a place as safe, easy and effortless, or complex and laborious, even generating uncertainty. While different platforms are used in digital spaces where the basic activities can be very similar, uncertainty is often felt when moving from a familiar platform to a new one. Once norms and routines have been established for using a specific digital space, a strong sense of familiarity brings certainty and ease to activities in the space. Transitions to new places may feel surprisingly difficult, and it is worth considering how to guide people and how people guide themselves into new digital spaces.

The following table presents the scanning tool statements for the next two dimensions of the experience of place: task and tale (Table 3).

Table 3 The statements connected to task and tie of the physical or digital experience of place

#	Focus	PHYSICAL	DIGITAL
5	6TX	The furniture is nice and functional <i>here</i> .	The icons are easy to understand and use.
6	6TX	The technical equipment is easy to take in use.	<i>The environment</i> provides me help when needed.
7	6TX	It is good to study <i>here</i> together.	The tasks conducted <i>here</i> motivate me.
8	6TX	I can study and do my tasks alone <i>here</i> .	<i>The digital environment</i> supports my learning by providing feedback.

Tale and theme of place

Tale, the fifth dimension of the 6T model, also describes the experience of place. What kind of narratives do places tell their users? Narratives can describe a school brand, and they can be

visible and uniform, or they can be stories that provoke conflicting ideas. What is interesting is whether learners can feel that they are part of the stories that places convey. Narratives of place come alive when people talk about places, sharing experiences of visiting them or working in them. Narratives conveyed to visitors or learners in the place may be based on conscious choices about the atmosphere, tempo, familiarity and functionality of the place. Narratives of place can also be told by things whose significance has gone unnoticed and have hence been overlooked. They can become precisely the experiences learners remember and describe as their experiences. Narratives of place can attract people to return to or avoid places in the future. Experience shows that digital environments do not generate narratives of place similarly to physical spaces. In fact, the narrative nature of digital environments can be seen as a dimension of the experience of place that opens new opportunities, resulting in places that generate positive imprints, convey consistent stories and attract users.

The sixth dimension of the 6T model is learners’ experience of the significance of place. They may consider whether they consider learning environments their own, whether they are happy to visit them and what makes these environments important to them. The way in which places are maintained also indicate their significance. A range of elements of significance can be observed when examining various spaces. In school, breaks in the fresh open air support learning, which can have great significance in the experience of place. Places can contain furniture important to users, such as a small reading corner in the classroom. The ways in which places support learners as individuals to be exactly what they wish to be also illustrates the importance of places to learners. Digital spaces too can be furnished with things that are important to users. Experiences of the significance of place to learners can be produced, for example, through the support available or by arranging the place with features that support learning.

The following table presents statements related to narratives and significance in both physical and digital environments (Table 4).

Table 3 Statements connected to tale and theme of the physical or digital experience of place

#	Focus	PHYSICAL	DIGITAL
9	6TX	I will remember <i>this place</i> for a long time.	I will remember <i>this environment</i> for a long time.
10	6TX	I want to send a selfie to my friend <i>from here</i> .	I want to share <i>this link with</i> my friends.
11	6TX	I want to come <i>here</i> soon again.	I want to use <i>this digital environment</i> soon again.
12	6TX	<i>This</i> is an engaging environment.	<i>This</i> is an engaging environment.

3.3 Co-used learning and innovation environments

Collaborative sharing is related to some parties having resources beyond their own needs, enabling them to lend resources to others. In physical learning and innovation environments, such resources can be, for example, spaces vacated on university campuses or facilities used less in the evenings or summer terms. This means that users are granted temporary access to products or services, while their ownership remains with the original owners (access over ownership). Shared use and collaborative sharing have a range of forms, platforms and uses. For example, a booking calendar and personal apartment numbers are used to book a common laundry room. In this example, the primary goal of users is to wash their clothes instead of gaining access to the washing machine itself. General upper secondary school students who

use university facilities on campus not only gain access to laboratories, sports facilities and other special facilities, but also the opportunity to collaborate with the university and expose themselves to academic culture, which helps them progress in their studies even when transferring from one level of education to another (Luostarinen et al. 2024). Startups and other users of shared facilities expect below-market rents but also wish to be close to other like-minded startups as well as the university community, including researchers, students and university facilities (Wang et al. 2024). Co-consumption and shared use emerge strongly alongside many other phenomena associated with shared use, and their models are increasingly utilised in the promotion of the circular economy. These have been investigated at Aalto University (e.g., Luostarinen et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2024).

The statements pertaining to collaborative sharing are built for two respondent groups: 1) users, or learners and organisations who consume collaboratively shared services for a possible service fee, and 2) service providers who enable shared use. In both cases, the statements are structured around three themes of sharing, each of which can be interpreted as sharing strategy. These strategies are aimed at the resource-efficient use of space. In addition, separate statements for collaborative sharing have been created for physical and digital learning and innovation environments.

A strategy of reduction means that fewer materials are consumed per user. Shared products are consumed by many users concurrently or in turns, making it unnecessary for everyone to have a new product of their own. The amount of material consumed per product is not necessarily reduced as a whole, but rather per person. The number of products needed is nevertheless smaller, as they are in shared use.

A prolonging strategy in the public built environment indicates that facilities or buildings are better maintained through basic maintenance and repairs, thus extending their useful life. In this case, 'useful life' refers to the utilisation rate of shared-use facilities. In other words, useful life does not mean how long such facilities remain available even if they are not used. Typically, more intensive shared use requires professional maintenance practices to keep facilities in fit-for-purpose condition. Since shared use encourages the deployment of careful maintenance and repair measures, the useful life of facilities is also extended.

A strategy of reuse indicates that shared use replaces the need to own the product in question. In such cases, the production of entirely new products is reduced by making the consumption and acquisition of used products as effortless as possible. After their use, the next user can use the product according to the principles of shared use or concurrently with others, depending on the product.

Tables 5 and 6 describe the shared-use statements from the perspectives of users (learners) as well as (paying) organisations and service providers. Statements can be chosen for user surveys depending on the facility or service features.

Table 4 Statements for the physical learning environment – perspectives of user and provider

#	Focus	To user or user organisation	To service provider
1	PHYS	I/We co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> for its easy accessibility.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space accommodating our service</i> is consumed via sharing without transferring ownership.

2	PHYS	I/We co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> for its flexible use to meet my/our needs.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space accommodating our service</i> is designed for multiple purposes, rather than a single purpose.
3	PHYS	I/We co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> to benefit from its cost savings.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed for repeated use, rather than just once.
4	PHYS	I/We co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> as it requires less commitment than ownership.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed to be maintained to prolong its use.
5	PHYS	I/We co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> as I/we perceive the sharing to be more sustainable than ownership.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed to be reused, remanufactured, or/and recycled at the end of its current lifecycle.
6	PHYS	I/we co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> as I/we trust the quality of the service or system it provides.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed to be applied in multiple locations.
7	PHYS	I/we co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> as I trust the people I/we co-use it with.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> provides training, guidance and/or information on its co-use.
8	PHYS	I/we co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> to be part of a group or community I/we find beneficial.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed to support communities.
9	PHYS	I/we co-use <i>the shared physical learning and innovation space</i> because of the sense of belonging it gives me/us.	<i>The physical learning and innovation space</i> is designed to support the feeling of belonging.

Table 6 Statements for digital learning environment – perspectives of user and provider.

#	Focus	To user or user organisation	To service provider
1	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> for its easy accessibility.	<i>The hardware of our service</i> is consumed via sharing without transferring ownership.
2	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> for its flexible use to meet my/our needs.	<i>The hardware and software of our service</i> are designed for multiple purposes, rather than a single purpose.

3	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> to benefit from its cost savings.	<i>The hardware and software of our service</i> are designed for repeated use, rather than just once.
4	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> as it requires less commitment than ownership.	<i>The hardware of our service</i> is designed to be maintained to prolong its use.
5	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> as I/we perceive the sharing to be more sustainable than ownership.	<i>The hardware of our service</i> is designed to be reused, remanufactured, or/and recycled at the end of its current lifecycle.
6	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> as I trust the quality of <i>the service or system</i> it provides.	<i>The hardware of our service</i> is designed to be used in multiple locations.
7	DIG	I/We co-use <i>the shared hardware of the service</i> as I/we trust the people I co-use it with.	<i>Our service</i> provides training, guidance and/or information on its co-use.
8	DIG	I/We (co-)use <i>the service including hardware and software</i> to be part of a group or community I/we find beneficial.	<i>Our service</i> is designed to support communities.
9	DIG	I/We (co-)use <i>the service</i> because of the sense of belonging it gives me/us.	<i>Our service</i> is designed to support a feeling of belonging.

4. How to use the JAVIST scanning tool

The development of digital and physical learning and innovation environments provokes the following questions, among others:

- Are all the necessary elements for the learning and innovation environment in place?
- Have we forgotten something essential?
- What does it look like from the user perspective?
- Is it possible to add something from the perspective of shared use and sharing practices?

The JAVIST scanning tool helps you in the development of your service or product: it enables you to create a baseline and lay down a development path for your service or product. You can also use it to collect feedback on your service or product. The JAVIST scanning tool can be used as part of the PDCA principle and operating model for continuous improvement. The model, whose name stands for Plan, Do, Check and Act, is visually depicted in Figure 4. Activities are planned and carried out in accordance with the agreed goals. Activities are assessed, measured and developed based on the feedback received. The review of goals and the development of activities are seen as a continuous process where the goals set are nearer after each development round.

Figure 4 PDCA-principle: visualization of cyclic process.

The scanning tool developed in the Resourceful Sharing project helps integrate several dimensions into a single solution. However, the tool is not a certificate, but rather a checklist. The business representatives involved in the development of the tool sought a solution that is easy to understand, which is why the statements used are brief and unambiguous.

The JAVIST scanning tool is easily accessible. It is an openly available practice developed collaboratively with businesses and researchers, which contributes to promoting multiprofessional collaboration in the development of learning and innovation environments. The tool can be adapted to user needs, and statements relevant to specific circumstances can be selected from among the selection.

Using the tool in customer surveys

When you wish to develop your service or product using the JAVIST scanning tool, take these steps:

1. Download the statements included in the tool as an Excel file from the [project's Zenodo page](https://zenodo.org/communities/javist) (zenodo.org/communities/javist).
2. Read the statements and analyse which of them are appropriate for scanning your product / service. You can remove, add or edit statements. In the template, the topic being evaluated is referred to generically as “innovation”, “service”, or “learning environment”. You can replace this word with the name of your own product/service. Editing may be necessary if you are conducting the survey with different target groups, among other aspects. For example, some statements may be more appropriate for users of the innovation or the learning environment, while others may suit individuals responsible for purchasing your product/service. The statements are designed for surveying the views of adolescents and adults. If the target group is elementary school pupils or younger, you can, for example, replace the numerical scale with smiley faces.
3. The Excel template includes notes and color codes added by the authors. Once you've modified the statements to suit your needs, remove any markings that are unnecessary for the respondent and renumber the statements if needed (for example, if you've removed or rearranged some of them). Ensure that the formatting is consistent throughout the document.
4. Print the questionnaire or import it to the survey service you are using (e.g., Microsoft or Google Forms).

5. Collect, analyse and report on data using the methods you have chosen.

The focus of the statement sets vary slightly. The experienced significance of learning is surveyed through 20 statements. The set of statements for the experience of place in learning environments includes 12 statements, and they can be chosen in accordance with their relevance to the physical or digital experience of place. Nine statements are provided for shared service use and the practices of shared use. They too have been designed for both physical and digital learning environments. A set of statements is also available for user or service provider organisations. The descriptions are summarised in Table 7.

Table 7 Summary of set of statements and perspectives.

Focus	The experienced relevance of learning	Experience of places for learning	Co-use and sharing of service in physical and digital learning environments
Number of statements	20	6 + 6	9 + 9
Perspectives	Personal relevance Vocational relevance Societal relevance	Tune (atmosphere) and tempo of the experience of physical or digital place Task (functionality) and tie (familiarity) of the experience of physical or digital place Tale (narrative) and theme (significance) of the experience of physical or digital place	Perspective of user / user organization or service provider in physical learning environment Perspective of user / user organization or service provider in digital learning environment
Other notions	No optional sets of statements Negative statements	Optional sets of statements No negative statements	Optional sets of statements No negative statements

While most of the statements are in the affirmative, some are negative. These are visualised with the marking “negat.”. Negative statements are included because they can be used to exclude respondents who have generically selected the same response to each statement. It is worth noting that not all statements are necessarily suited for investigating specific products by individual businesses. In such cases, unsuitable statements must be removed at the preparatory stage, while the term indicated in blue must be replaced with the name of your

business's product or service. Statements whose identifier is indicated in the second column of the table are classified by dimensions of relevance:

- Personal relevance (PR)
- Societal relevance (SR)
- Vocational relevance (VC)

The identifier for the six-dimensional experience of place in the second column is 6TX (experience). In terms of sharing, the identifier for physical learning environments is PHYS and for digital learning environments DIG.

Using the tool in product development workshops

In addition to surveys, the tool can be used to structure the content of workshops organised for product development purposes. These workshops can examine services or products from the selected perspectives of the JAVIST scanning tool. Workshops can also be used to develop existing services. Convening to discuss a specific theme indicates the importance of the matter and contributes to engaging the workshop participants. When planning workshops, you should define their purpose, participants and goals. What results are expected, and how will they be exploited?

At the beginning of the workshop, review its goals and content – why and how are we here? You should also provide background information. People often want to cram too much content into individual workshops. It is also important to appropriately target the workshop and know the participating target groups, as well as the themes important to them.

Three desks can be organised for the workshop: one for relevance, one for experience and one for sharing and shared use. The statements for the themes are provided at the desks, with facilitators at each desk encouraging participants to assess the service or product from these specific perspectives: how the aspects presented in the statements are realised, what their significance is and what measures emerge for their development. When planning the desks, you should focus on the experience of place from the perspective of the physical or digital environment. In the statements for sharing, the perspectives of users or the service provider should also be included.

Picture 1. Completion of the three desk assignments in the JAVIST workshop.

Picture 2. Methods can include both traditional facilitation methods, such as sticky notes, and digital tools, such as online questionnaires.

Picture 3. At the JAVIST safari, the desks were named Lion, Elephant and Tiger instead of numbers.

At the end of the workshop, important questions for the organiser to consider include the following: Were all the tasks completed? Is more information needed? Is there a need for another workshop? Finally, it is important to consider the form in which the results are summarised and with whom the summary is shared, so that the impact and the message go hand in hand.

6. How was JAVIST scanning tool developed?

In addition to multidisciplinary researcher collaboration, collaboration with various businesses developing products and services for learning and innovation environments has played a key role in the Resourceful Sharing project. The development of the tool progressed through two parallel processes. In the researcher process, experts in the used and responsible built environment as well as science education met on a regular basis, developing a common framework of reference, a set of statements and a manual.

In the parallel process, workshops with businesses were organised every few months to test the various elements of the tool. The first workshop was held in March 2024, with a total of three workshops organised by the end of the year. In the spring, a joint review of statements related to the experience of place and the relevance of learning was organised, and in August a similar review was carried out on statements related to shared use. In the next stage, all of the statements were commented on.

Picture 4. Among others, startups in the educational technology sector contributed to the development of the scanning tool together with university researchers.

Picture 5. Workshop outcomes included discussions between business representatives and university researchers. The researchers received direct feedback from businesses on what works in the tool and what is not needed.

Picture 6. In the workshops, businesses had the opportunity to network and access the latest research-based knowledge, while enjoying tasty refreshments.

7. Examples and uses of the JAVIST scanning tool

The following are three examples of using the JAVIST scanning tool to develop an innovation or learning environment. Actual use cases can inspire other businesses to deploy the tool as part of their product development.

Use case 1

JAVIST scanning tool for innovation environment ideas – Has everything been taken into consideration?

Need: Service providers wanted to test the concept of a collaboratively shared workspace before deployment. The service concept was designed by incorporating facility booking, booking details and invoicing into a single application. Technical development had partially taken the attention off from user orientation.

Goal: To ensure that the service concept considers all aspects relevant to the experience of place

Action: The service providers and external facilitators examined the plan from the perspective of the user journey: arrival and working in the space, transitions in the space and departure from the space were discussed separately, and each stage was assessed through the six dimensions of the experience of place. The participants first completed an independent assessment, on the basis of which a joint discussion took place.

Result: The findings exposed challenges between the desired and possible realities, particularly in terms of transitions between places. Familiarity to users and the new concept were not necessarily thoroughly thought out. In addition, assessment of the significance of the place emphasised a feeling of collaboration present or created in the space, as well as a feeling of its importance. This also contributes to the narrative of place. The tool helped reveal what is known

as invisible information related to user experience. By exploiting this information, the entire concept was able to be enhanced already at the brainstorming stage.

Use case 2

JAVIST scanning tool for testing solutions before releasing them to wider audiences

Need: A business has developed an AI-powered bird identification application. Based on teacher testing, there appears to be a great need for such an app, but the learner experience is yet to be studied.

Goal: The business wants to know whether learners consider the app developed and the avian context relevant.

Action: The business provides a teacher with the app for a two-week trial. During this period, the curriculum encompasses ecology, bird biology and species identification. The business trains the teacher to use the app and helps in planning meaningful learning content. In addition, a workshop is organised for learners to ensure that they are familiar with the technical aspects of the app. The teacher then implements the bird module, and the learners' notions of using the app are studied using the relevance component of the scanning tool.

Result: The scanning tool demonstrates that learners perceive AI-powered bird identification as a modern way of studying avian traits. At the same time, they learn to understand the significance of biology as part of a sustainable future and demonstrate a personal interest in the school subject. As no actual vocational relevance was perceived, it can be boosted in the app by adding content that, for example, introduces career options for biologists.

User case 3

JAVIST scanning tool for collecting feedback on solutions and focusing on continuous improvement

Need: The City of Helsinki's TEKLA testbed piloted its operations in spring 2024. The mobile experimental container TEKLA is an entirely new kind of learning space. In TEKLA, learners and teachers have the opportunity to participate in interesting workshops where new learning technologies under development are being tested.

Goal: To collect information on the user experience

Action: Only one of each pair of statements for the experience of place was used to collect user feedback, as the aim was to collect feedback quickly from the entire user group after the workshop. The respondents ranged from kindergarteners to ninth graders. The statements were read to the pre-primary and primary education learners, and they chose their answers from among emojis. Learners who were able to read and write responded independently to the written statements.

Result: The experiential container produces memorable experiences. The results confirmed that the innovative space/innovation was successful. In this case, the tool did not highlight specific development targets. As feedback providers, the children did not specifically bring forward development needs, but the situation looks different from the perspective of adults. The supervisor in the container observed the situation throughout the workshop and was able to

immediately intervene and guide the activities. The tool served here as a source of information on the user experience.

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Appendices

A stylised example from the JAVIST scanning survey

Dear Respondent

You have been invited to participate in this survey. The purpose of the survey is to analyse the perceived relevance of the *MunOpinto* application and the suitability of its digital learning environment for use in school education. At the same time, we aim to examine the co-use of *MunOpinto* devices in schools as a shared resource.

No personal data is collected in the study, and all materials will be confidential and securely stored. The data will only be used internally to further develop the *MunOpinto* products.

Thank you for considering participation in this research. Completing the survey will take approximately 10 minutes.

For more information, please contact:

Sales Specialist, +358 50 123 1234; sales.specialist@company.com

I understand the research purpose and data processing.

I am willing to participate in the study: YES ___ or NO ___.

Response scale

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

#	Statements for the pupils to answer.	1	2	3	4	5
1	While using MunOpinto app I learned things that helped me better understand the topics taught at school.					
2	While using MunOpinto app I learned things that will be useful to me in the future.					
3	I think MunOpinto app was difficult to use.					
4	I learned teamwork skills while using MunOpinto app.					

5	Using MunOpinto app did not teach me any new skills.					
6	MunOpinto app gave me new information about jobs in the field.					
7	I will use MunOpinto app in my future studies or profession.					
8	Using MunOpinto app is useless for me in the future.					
9	Using the MultiLearning app includes creative work.					
#	Statements for the pupils to answer.	1	2	3	4	5
10	MunOpinto app looks inviting.					
11	The icons are easy to understand and use.					
12	MunOpinto app provides me help when needed.					
13	The tasks conducted in MunOpinto app motivate me.					
14	I will remember MunOpinto app for a long time					
15	I want to use MunOpinto app soon again.					
#	Statements for the persons responsible for the purchases.	1	2	3	4	5
16	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app to benefit from its cost savings.					
17	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app as it requires less commitment than ownership.					
18	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app as we perceive the sharing to be more sustainable than ownership.					
19	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app as we trust the quality of the service it provides.					
20	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app as I trust the people we co-use it with.					
21	We co-use the shared hardware for MunOpinto app to be part of a group or community we find beneficial.					

Thank you for participating in the study.